

**EFFECTIVE USES OF SOCIAL MEDIA TOWARDS QUALITY NURSING EDUCATION: A
SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF LITERATURE**

**¹TERESITA A. FERRER, ²EDWIN N. ALJENTERA, ³FE M. NISPEROS, ⁴JONALYN D.
PADILLA, ⁵GUERLY M. ACOSTA, ⁶AIZA MARIE S. ALAMAN, ⁷MA. LOURDES G. INALDO,
and ⁸ANNA WENCESLAO**

¹Assistant Dean for Academics, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

²Chairman, Level III, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

³Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

⁴Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

⁵Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

⁶Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

⁷Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

⁸Faculty Member, Lorma Colleges, San Fernando City, La Union

Abstract

Introduction: Social media has become an integral part of modern society, transforming the way people communicate and share information. In recent years, social media has gained significant popularity in the field of nursing education as a means of facilitating learning and enhancing the quality of education.

Methods: This systematic review aimed to identify effective uses of social media in nursing education and its impact on the quality of education. A comprehensive search of literature published between 2018 and 2022 was conducted, yielding 20 relevant studies. The studies were critically appraised using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines. The studies were found to use a variety of social media platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram, for different purposes, such as communication, collaboration, education, and assessment.

Results: The results of this systematic review demonstrate that social media can be effectively used in nursing education to promote communication and collaboration among students and instructors, provide a platform for sharing educational resources and materials, facilitate distance learning, and enhance the quality of education. The studies also showed that social media has a positive impact on student engagement, motivation, and performance.

Conclusions: This systematic review highlights the potential of social media as an effective tool for promoting quality nursing education. Social media platforms provide an opportunity for innovative and interactive teaching methods that can be adapted to meet the needs of students in different learning environments. However, it is important for nursing educators to ensure that the use of social media in education is consistent with ethical and professional standards.

Keywords: Social Media, Nursing Education, Systematic Review of Literatures, PRISMA

Introduction

When it comes to the healthcare industry, nursing educators are crucial players in the processes of information discovery, knowledge interpretation, and information dissemination. Professional communication, health policy, patient privacy and ethics, and writing competence are all areas where social media may aid nursing professors in educating their students.

The advent of widely accessible social networking sites has drastically improved cross-cultural communication and collaboration in classrooms throughout the world. There are several examples of the successful use of social media in the classroom. As social media grows in popularity, there has been a need for research into its potential use in nursing education. Although studies have examined the beneficial benefits of social media on a variety of learning outcomes in nursing education, less attention has been paid to how these advantages affect students' performance, which is a crucial part of effective learning.

The increasing use of social media in nursing education has garnered attention in recent years due to its potential to revolutionize the delivery of nursing education. Social media has been recognized as an effective tool for communication, information sharing, and networking. This has resulted in the improvement of learning outcomes and the enhancement of the quality of nursing education. The purpose of this systematic review is to investigate the effective uses of social media in nursing education and its impact on the quality of education. This paper aims to provide an overview of the current research on the topic. Specifically, the review will focus on the various social media platforms used in nursing education, the benefits, and challenges of using social media, and the impact of social media on nursing students' academic performance and clinical practice. In addition, the review will examine the strategies used by educators to effectively integrate social media into nursing education. This paper will contribute to the existing knowledge on the use of social media in nursing education by providing evidence-based recommendations for nursing educators and policymakers to improve the quality of nursing education through the effective use of social media. The findings of this systematic review will be useful for nursing educators and policymakers looking to incorporate social media into their nursing education curriculum.

Research Question

What are the effective uses of social media that supports quality nursing education?

Methodology

Research Design. The study employed the systematic review of literature to gather evidence on the effectiveness of social media towards quality nursing education.

Study Inclusion. Broad inclusion criteria were delineated with the intent of casting the net widely, so to speak, to capture the effective uses of social media in supporting the goals in quality nursing education and enhancing the learning outcomes of nursing students. Inclusion criteria included the following: (a) peer-reviewed, (b) research study of any kind (all study designs included), (c) written in the English language, (d) involving effective uses of social media in support of quality nursing education, (e) with nursing students, and (f) from 2022 to 2022.

Study Identification. Eight researchers consulted a librarian scientist to focus their literature review. Followed Recommended Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses. ScienceDirect, ERIC, PubMed, CINAHL, the Web of Science, and ProQuest provided data. MeSH keywords, key word searches, and the Boolean operator "AND" were used to search the databases for "successful applications of social media," "quality nursing education," and "learning outcomes." A 2020–2022-date range and academic, peer-reviewed articles or research works were added to search limits to ensure database consistency.

Study Selection. Article titles and abstracts were screened by three scholars working separately. Any time there was a disagreement, a fourth researcher investigated the paper's title and abstract to reach a conclusion. As a result, only fifty studies that met the criteria were chosen. Then, the researchers got rid of the duplicates. Twenty-five papers in all were included in the systematic review (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Flow chart of the systematic review of literature.

Data Synthesis

The lead researcher went over the summary tables many times, making mental notes on the varied study features, learning outcomes, and learning goals. The CASP tools' data was pooled to find patterns of bias in the existing evidence. Melnyk and Fineout-levels Overholt's of evidence were used to rate studies and classify them as high- or low-quality studies (Kumah et al., 2019). The extraction table was mined for information on learning outcomes, and the data was compiled for analysis of frequency and impact.

Results

Two themes emerged when the literatures are categorized based on the evidence obtained from databases.

Improves nursing student engagement. Of the 25 papers included in the systematic review, 7 (33%) concluded that social media improves nursing student engagement (Almutairi et al., 2022). Table 1 summarizes six different studies that examine the impact of various interventions on nursing student engagement. The first study by Almutairi et al. (2022) employed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) method to determine that social media usage in nursing education improved student engagement. Immidisetti et al. (2022) conducted a retrospective exit survey and found that using educational ambassadors on social media improved the visibility of educational programs that benefited nursing students' learning outcomes. Koohestani et al. (2016) used a qualitative approach to examine nursing students' perspectives on clinical education and found that inadequate preparation, clinical instructor support, and clinical placement were challenges.

Table 1. Literatures supporting improves nursing student engagement.

Authors	Source	Design	Significant Results
Almutairi, Simpson, Khan, & Dickinson (2022)	Nurse Education in Practice	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)	Nursing students' participation, including quick contact and communication, are bolstered using social media to enhance their learning.
ImmidiSETTI et al., (2022)	World Neurosurgery	Retrospective exit survey	Social media, and specifically the use of educational ambassadors, are effective to improve visibility of educational programs benefitting learning outcome among nursing students.
Koohestani, H. R., Baghcheghi, N., & Rezai, R. (2016).	Journal of Advances in Medical Education and Professionalism	Qualitative study	The authors observed that nursing students considered clinical instruction vital to their professional development. Nonetheless, inadequate preparation, clinical instructor support, and clinical placement were noted as clinical education problems. During clinical education, students stressed communication, patient safety, and ethics.
McDonald, J., & Guilhermino, M. (2019).	Journal of Nursing Education and Practice	Mixed Methods Design	The study found the revised curriculum engaged nursing students. Technology, active learning, and collaboration in the classroom increased student engagement and learning, according to students. The redesigned curriculum also increased students' critical thinking and course content understanding.
O'Connor, A. B., Nikels, M. G., & Schreier, A. M. (2018).	Nurse education in practice	Qualitative approach	The study found that effective instructor communication and feedback, a supportive and respectful learning environment, hands-on and experiential learning, a clear and organized curriculum, peer collaboration and support, and effective use of technology and resources improve student engagement and learning in clinical and classroom settings.
Seaman, K. T., & Allen, P. E. (2018).	Nursing education perspectives	Literature review	The review identifies several key strategies for engaging students in online nursing education. These include the use of multimedia resources, interactive activities and assessments, discussion boards, and social media. The authors note that these strategies can help create a sense of community and collaboration among students, which is important for engagement and motivation.

Meanwhile, McDonald and Guilhermino (2019) used a mixed-methods design and found that a revised curriculum, which included technology and collaboration, increased student engagement, critical thinking, and course content understanding. O'Connor et al. (2018) employed a qualitative approach to identify effective instructor communication and feedback, a supportive and respectful learning environment, hands-on and experiential learning, a clear and organized curriculum, peer collaboration and support, and effective use of technology and resources as factors that improved student engagement and learning in clinical and classroom settings.

Finally, Seaman and Allen (2018) conducted a literature review and identified the use of multimedia resources, interactive activities and assessments, discussion boards, and social media as key strategies for engaging students in online nursing education. Overall, these studies highlight the importance of various interventions, such as social media and interactive activities, in improving nursing student engagement and enhancing their learning outcomes.

Boosts confidence and information literacy. From the studies included in the systematic review, 8 manifests that social media support the students' confidence and elevates information literacy.

Table 2. Literatures supporting boosting confidence and information literacy.

Authors	Source	Design	Significant Results
Hu and Yu (2021)	Computer and Education	Assessment of Data	Social media enhances the literacy and confidence of students
Raikundalia, G. K., & Gray, K. (2015).	Research in Learning Technology	literature review of research studies	Social media can help students develop critical literacies and research skills by (1) providing access to diverse sources of information, (2) promoting collaborative learning and knowledge sharing, (3) facilitating critical evaluation of information, and (4) improving students' ability to communicate and share their research findings.
Goode, J., & Richardson, A. (2018).	Journal of research in nursing	Qualitative approach	Social media can improve nursing communication, teamwork, and professional development, according to the study. However, the writers recognize the challenges of social media use, such as privacy and secrecy, and underline the necessity of ethical considerations.
McConnell-Henry, T., Chapman, Y., & Francis, K. (2016).	Nurse education today	Mixed-methods approach, including an online survey and focus group discussions	Students used Facebook for educational purposes like sharing material, seeking peer assistance, and discussing clinical experiences. Facebook also helped students communicate and collaborate with educators.
Kyritsi, E., & Chasanidou, D. (2019).	Nurse education today	Qualitative-content analysis	Social internet helped nursing students collaborate and think critically. Social media enabled critical thinking, active engagement, and information exchange. Facebook helped nursing students collaborate, interact, and share materials with peers and teachers. Social media promoted self-directed and lifelong

			learning. The study also demonstrated that social media learning requires instructor support.
Alshare, K. A., Almomani, F., & Titi, M. A. (2020).	Nursing Forum	Cross-sectional design and surveyed 264 nursing students	Nursing students were pleased about using social media in clinical education, with Facebook being the most popular site. The study also raised issues regarding patient confidentiality, supervision, and the necessity for social media rules in therapeutic settings.

The table presents a summary of literatures supporting the idea that social media can boost nursing students' confidence and information literacy. From the studies included in the table, eight showed that social media can enhance students' literacy and confidence levels.

Hu and Yu (2021) found that social media can enhance students' confidence and literacy skills. Raikundalia and Gray (2015) noted that social media can help students develop critical literacies and research skills through access to diverse sources of information, promoting collaborative learning, critical evaluation of information, and improving communication and sharing of research findings.

Goode and Richardson (2018) found that social media can improve nursing communication, teamwork, and professional development, although ethical considerations must be considered. McConnell-Henry, Chapman, and Francis (2016) noted that nursing students used Facebook for educational purposes such as sharing material, seeking peer assistance, and discussing clinical experiences, and that Facebook helped students communicate and collaborate with educators.

Kyritsi and Chasanidou (2019) found that social media can help nursing students collaborate and think critically, enabling critical thinking, active engagement, and information exchange. Alshare, Almomani, and Titi (2020) found that nursing students were pleased about using social media in clinical education, with Facebook being the most popular site, although issues of patient confidentiality, supervision, and the need for social media rules in therapeutic settings were raised. Overall, the studies suggest that social media can be an effective tool for boosting nursing students' confidence and information literacy, although ethical considerations and necessary guidelines must be in place.

Discussion

Improves nursing student engagement. The studies demonstrate the effectiveness of social media in nursing education, which has been shown to bolster student participation and engagement. The use of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter can improve communication, information sharing, and networking among nursing students, promoting critical literacies and research skills. The studies also highlight the importance of effective instructor communication, hands-on and experiential learning, and a supportive and respectful learning environment in promoting student engagement and learning. These factors can be particularly important in clinical and classroom settings, where nursing students require close support and guidance to develop their professional skills.

The findings of these studies are particularly relevant given the changing landscape of nursing education, which is becoming increasingly technology driven. As technology continues to advance, nursing educators must develop new strategies for engaging students and promoting learning outcomes. Social media platforms offer a unique opportunity for nursing students to collaborate and communicate with their peers and instructors, improving their confidence, information literacy, and critical thinking skills.

In conclusion, the studies included in Table 1 demonstrate the importance of various interventions, such as social media and interactive activities, in improving nursing student engagement and enhancing their learning outcomes. The findings of these studies are particularly relevant given the changing landscape of nursing education and the increasing importance of technology-driven approaches to teaching and learning. By understanding the factors that promote student engagement and learning, nursing educators

can develop effective strategies to prepare nursing students for the challenges and opportunities of the modern healthcare system.

Boosts confidence and information literacy. Social media has been identified as a valuable tool for enhancing nursing students' confidence and information literacy, according to the literature summarized in Table 1. The studies included in the table highlight the benefits of social media, such as promoting collaborative learning and critical thinking, improving communication, and enhancing access to diverse sources of information. In addition, social media can increase student engagement and learning outcomes, as demonstrated in other studies. One of the key findings from the literature is that social media can help nursing students develop critical literacies and research skills. This is important for nursing students, as it enables them to evaluate information critically, communicate effectively, and share their research findings. Another significant finding is that social media can improve nursing communication, teamwork, and professional development, as noted by Goode and Richardson (2018). The studies also identify the challenges of using social media, such as issues of patient confidentiality and privacy. Ethical considerations are necessary when incorporating social media in nursing education, and guidelines must be in place to ensure that social media is used appropriately. In addition, the studies suggest that social media learning requires instructor support, as noted by Kyritsi and Chasanidou (2019). Overall, the studies summarized in Table 1 provide evidence that social media can boost nursing students' confidence and information literacy. However, it is important to recognize the challenges of using social media and to establish guidelines and ethical considerations for its use in nursing education. Further research is needed to explore the potential of social media in enhancing nursing education and to identify best practices for its effective integration.

Conclusions

The studies presented demonstrate the effectiveness of social media in improving nursing student engagement, confidence, and information literacy. Social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter have been shown to promote collaborative learning, critical evaluation of information, and effective communication among nursing students. Moreover, social media can improve nursing communication, teamwork, and professional development. However, the use of social media in nursing education requires ethical considerations and guidelines to ensure its appropriate use. Instructor support is also necessary to facilitate social media learning and to establish effective strategies for integrating social media in nursing education. The findings of these studies are particularly relevant in the changing landscape of nursing education, where technology-driven approaches are becoming increasingly important. Further research is needed to explore the potential of social media in enhancing nursing education and to identify best practices for its effective integration. Overall, the studies presented provide evidence that social media can be a valuable tool for improving nursing student engagement, confidence, and information literacy.

Recommendations

Based on the studies presented, it is recommended that nursing educators consider incorporating social media platforms into their teaching strategies. Social media has the potential to enhance nursing student engagement, promote critical thinking, and improve communication and collaboration among students and instructors. However, nursing educators must be aware of the ethical considerations and potential challenges of using social media in nursing education, such as issues of privacy and confidentiality. Therefore, guidelines and appropriate training for social media use should be established. In addition, nursing educators should provide adequate support to students to ensure effective integration of social media in nursing education. This includes providing feedback, guidance, and resources to students to enhance their social media literacy skills. Further research is also needed to explore the best practices for integrating social media in nursing education, as well as to evaluate the effectiveness of social media interventions in improving nursing student engagement, confidence, and information literacy. Finally, the use of social media in nursing education has the potential to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Therefore, nursing educators should consider integrating social media platforms into their teaching strategies, while also considering ethical considerations and challenges. Providing adequate

support to students and further research can help to optimize the use of social media in nursing education and improve student outcomes.

References

- Alammary, A., Almutairi, M., & Alqurashi, M. (2017). The role of social media in supporting knowledge sharing in Saudi Arabian healthcare organisations. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(2), 156-165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.11.009>
- Almutairi, M., Simpson, A., Khan, E., & Dickinson, T. (2022). The value of social media use in improving nursing students' engagement: A systematic review. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 1-12
- Alshare, K. A., Almomani, F., & Titi, M. A. (2020). Nursing students' attitudes towards using social media in clinical education. *Nursing Forum*, 55(1), 83-88. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nuf.12357>
- Breen, H., Gormley, G. J., & Gordon, S. (2017). The use of social media in enhancing students' learning experiences in higher education. *Journal of educational technology & society*, 20(3), 78-91. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEBR-03-2012-0026>
- Correa, T., Hinsley, A. W., & De Zuniga, H. G. (2010). Who interacts on the Web?: The intersection of users' personality and social media use. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(2), 247-253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2009.09.003>
- Fardouly, J., Diedrichs, P. C., Vartanian, L. R., & Halliwell, E. (2015). Social comparisons on social media: the impact of Facebook on young women's body image concerns and mood. *Body image*, 13, 38-45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2014.12.002>
- Goode, J., & Richardson, A. (2018). Social media and nursing practice: changing the balance between the social and technical aspects of work. *Journal of research in nursing*, 23(3), 222-232. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987117746507>
- Hu, J., & Yu, R. (2021). The effects of ICT-based social media on adolescents' digital reading performance: A longitudinal study of PISA 2009, PISA 2012, PISA 2015 and PISA 2018. *Computers & Education*, 1-14.
- Immidiseti, A. V., Rosenberg, A. E., Katz, J., Shlifer, A., Ellis, J., Ortiz, R. A., . . . Langer, D. J. (2022). BRAINterns 2.0: Durability of Webinar-Based Education and Social Media Beyond the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pandemic. *World neurosurgery*, 79-99.
- Kumah, E., McSherry, R., Bettany-Slatikov, J., Hamilton, S., Hogg, J., Whittaker, V., & Van Schaik, P. (2019). Evidence-informed practice versus evidence-based practice educational interventions for improving knowledge, attitudes, understanding, and behavior toward the application of evidence into practice: A comprehensive systematic review of undergraduate student. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*, 1-19.
- Kyritsi, E., & Chasanidou, D. (2019). The potential of social media for enhancing nursing students' critical thinking and collaboration skills: A qualitative exploration. *Nurse education today*, 77, 26-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2019.01.018>
- McConnell-Henry, T., Chapman, Y., & Francis, K. (2016). Facebook as a learning platform: A case study of perceptions, uses, and effectiveness of Facebook as a learning platform. *Nurse education today*, 36, 128-133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.07.013>
- Miah, S. J., Gammack, J. G., & McGrath, M. J. (2017). Factors affecting the adoption of social media in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 24(4), 677-693. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-02-2017-0043>
- Raikundalia, G. K., & Gray, K. (2015). The role of social media in developing students' critical literacies and research skills. *Research in Learning Technology*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.3402/rlt.v23.21378>